

Five adjectives to explain the whole personality: a brief scale of personality

Salvador Amigó

Departament de Personalitat, Avaluació i Tractaments Psicològics. Universitat de València
(Salvador.Amigo@uv.es)

Joan C. Micó

Institut Universitari de Matemàtica Pura i Aplicada. Universitat Politècnica de València
(jmico@mat.upv.es)

Antonio Caselles

Departament de Matemàtica Aplicada. Universitat de València
(Antonio.Caselles@uv.es)

Abstract

This study presents a brief scale of adjectives, the Five Adjective Scale (FAS) that attempts to assess one trait that defines the overall personality, the Unique Personality Trait. It is composed by five adjectives in trait-format of response. This scale presents adequate internal consistency and construct-validity. Moreover, the relationships with the personality factors of other models (Big Five and Big Three) are as expected. So, FAS is related positively with Extraversion, Psychoticism, Agreeableness and Openness, and negatively with Neuroticism and Conscientiousness. However, the FAS can integrate all of basic traits of personality.

1. Introduction

The existence of a single basic trait in the vertex of a hierarchy of personality traits: the Unique Trait Personality Theory (Amigó, 2005; Amigó, Caselles and Micó, 2008) has been proposed in literature.

This theory proposes that sensation seeking is a good approximation to the unique personality trait. From the Sensation Seeking Scale, composed by 12 adjectives, selected from the original Multiple Affect Adjective Check List (MAACL) by Zuckerman & Lubin (1965), we elaborated a brief scale of five adjectives. This is the Five Adjective Scale of Unique Trait Personality (FAS). We also use a list of 25 adjectives of personality that represent the Big Five (Extraversion, Neuroticism, Conscientiousness, Agreeableness and Openness). We use the trait-format for these two lists of adjectives.

We expect that FAS, as measure of the unique personality trait, is related with all of Big Five and the Big Three of the Eysenck's model (Eysenck & Eysenck, 1985).

2. Methodology

Subjects

A total of 206 subjects (70 males and 136 females) were included in the sample. These subjects were selected from the students and staff at the Universities of Valencia (100) and Valencian professionals of several types (106). The mean age was 32.79 (S.D.= 14.27) and the ages range from 17 to 74 years.

Instruments

1. EPQ-RS (Eysenck and Eysenck, 1985).
2. List of 25 adjectives of personality (Brody and Ehrlichman, 1998).
3. FAS: List of 5 adjectives, selected from the Sensation Seeking Scale (MAACL; Zuckerman & Lubin, 1965). **The adjectives are:** adventurous, daring, enthusiastic, merry and bored.

3. Results

The FAS presents adequate internal consistency and construct validity. The internal consistency of FAS is acceptable ($\alpha = .67$). A factor analysis was performed and a unique factor explaining 49.58 % of variance was obtained.

On the other hand, the relationships with the personality factors of other models (Big Five and Big Three) are as expected. Two regression analyses were performed, with FAS as a dependent variable. In the first analysis, the predictors were the big three (table 1), and in the second analysis, the predictors were the big five (table 2).

Variables	Beta	t	Sig.
Extraversion	.42	7.17	.000
Neuroticism	-.22	-3.76	.000
Psychoticism	.20	3.4	.001

Table 1. Regression analysis. Dependent variable: FAS.
Predictors: Big Three. Ajusted R-Square: .28

Variables	Beta	t	Sig.
Extraversion	.41	6.37	.000
Neuroticism	-.15	-2.93	.004
Agreeableness	.17	2.8	.006
Conscientiousness	-.13	-2.16	.031
Openness	.31	5.14	.000

Table 2. Regression analysis. Dependent variable: FAS
Predictors: Big Five. Ajusted R-Square: .42

4. Discussion

The FAS presents adequate internal consistency and construct validity, while the relationships with the personality factors of other models are as expected. All of the EPQ' traits are significant predictors of the AFS. Extraversion and Psychoticism with a beta positive and Neuroticism with a beta negative. With respect to the big five, all the traits are significant predictors. Extraversion, Agreeableness and Openness are positive predictors, and both Neuroticism and Conscientiousness are negative predictors. Therefore, this is a brief scale of adjectives that assess one trait that defines overall personality.

5. References

- Amigó, S. (2005). *La teoría del rasgo único de personalidad. Hacia una teoría unificada del cerebro y la conducta*. Editorial de la UPV: Valencia.
- Amigó, S., Caselles, A. and Micó, J.C. (2008). A dynamic extraversion model: the brain's response to a single dose of a stimulant drug. *British Journal of Mathematical and Statistical Psychology*, 61, 211–231.
- Brody, N. and Ehrlichman, H. (1998). *Personality Psychology. The Science of Individuality*. Prentice Hall, Inc.
- Eysenck, H.J. y Eysenck, M.W. (1985). *Personality and individual differences. A natural science approach*. New York: Plenum.
- Zuckerman, M., Lubin, B. & Rinck, C.M. (1983). Construction of new scales for the Múltiple Affect Adjective Check List. *Journal of Behavioral Assessment*, 5, 119-129.